

Are animals morally relevant beings?

**To what extent do Kant and Bentham's approaches to the moral
relevance of animals succeed?**

Extended essay

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Introduction

Up until the 17th century, philosophers regarded animals as being quite distinct from human beings; human beings had rationality whereas animals had none. This meant that animals had only instrumental value and could be used in any way that human beings desired. In the 18th century, Immanuel Kant further contributed to this view with his deontological ethics. However, as the Age of Enlightenment approached, Jeremy Bentham (1748-1820), a radical thinker, challenged this notion by asserting that animals possess intrinsic value and should be included in our moral framework. He contended that the capacity to suffer, rather than rationality, should be the basis for moral consideration.

In this essay, I will be comparing and contrasting these two philosophers' argument on the moral inclusivity of animals. I will begin by identifying the underlying assumptions of both philosophers and evaluating their validity. Next, I will delve into one of the key premises in Kant's argument, as it presents greater complexity compared to Bentham's. Following this, I will compare how each argument aligns with our moral intuitions and explore a few implications of their theories. I will also examine their connections to speciesism. Finally, I will conclude my essay and address the question: "Did they reach their desired conclusion?"

Bentham's Utilitarian Approach

As an utilitarian, Bentham believes in the greater good principal, which one should only act in such a way that the results of that act should produce the greatest amount of good for the greatest number. Since humans are naturally motivated to seek pleasure and avoid pain, these experiences should be the primary basis for determining what actions are morally right or wrong. In essence, all sentient creatures should be morally relevant due to their capacity of perceiving pleasure and pain. In turn, all other standards such as rationality, gender, and specie differences are completely insignificant in our moral decision making processes.

To justify this, Bentham raises an analogy of racism in his "Introduction to The Principles of Morals and Legislation" that "*The French have already discovered that the blackness of skin is no reason why a human being should be abandoned without redress to the caprice of a tormentor.*" (Bentham, 1789) He then consequently posits that, "*it may come one day to be*

recognized, that the number of the legs, the villosity of the skin, or the termination of the os sacrum, are reasons equally insufficient for abandoning a sensitive being to the same fate.”

(Bentham, 1823) Any denial of this idea is a potential defense for "speciesism"—the idea that a person’s treatment should be determined only by their status as a member of the human species. In fact, sheer prejudice for one's species might not be any more justified than prejudice for one's race. For instance, it is not easier to justify inflicting suffering on sentient non-human animals than it is to justify inflicting suffering on humans, as Bentham claims that "no reason can be given", meaning there isn't a valid explanation for why causing suffering to people is in any way worse than to non-human animals. Consequently, it is possible that speciesism is just as bad as racism, if not more so.

In the practice of utilitarianism in general, Bentham proposed seven different criteria for estimating the potential pleasure or pain of an act, which he termed the Hedonic Calculus: Intensity, duration, certainty, remoteness, fecundity, purity, and extent. Since pleasure and pain can be perceived by all sentient beings, it may be inferred that he expects this guideline to be implemented among animals as well, or at least our calculation of the “good” in our treatment of them. With the hedonic calculus, even if we are highly uncertain about the specific amount of happiness and suffering a particular animal can experience, we may still make an effort in roughly estimating it. Ultimately guiding our decisions about their treatment.

Kant’s Deontological Framework

While most ethical theories guide us to examine the external world, Kant’s framework encourages introspection. Kant’s deontological ethics emphasizes our recognition of moral duties rather than the consequences of our actions. For an action to be deemed moral, the individual must act for the sake of duty, instead of in accordance with it. Basically, if one’s actions are the complete opposite of their desires, such as if they want to beat a kid but suppressed themselves from doing so, they are acting for the sake of duty and that action can be morally praised. Thus, humans are considered the only moral agents not because we possess certain desires that compel us to act morally, but precisely because we are rational beings. Kant furthurs this argument claiming that as rational beings, humans possess the fundamental worth that is based on our autonomy and moral agency. These traits, in particular, grants us self governing capabilities,

enabling us to act regardless of our personal goals and desires, also known as following the Categorical Imperatives--rules that are universal, absolute and unconditional for all people (e.g. Thou shalt help others in need).

Kant argues that unlike animals, moral agents possess the capacity to "stand back" and reflect on our actions and their underlying motivations. While humans, like every other species, may experience emotions and desires, and in turn, biases, these subjective elements are completely irrelevant to moral decision makings. Instead, moral actions must stem from rational deliberation and respect for moral law. Based on this reasoning, animals should not be morally relevant as they do not possess the rational capacity to either obligate or be obligated. For example, if a grown-up tortures a pig extensively, he has not done that pig wrong. Because the pig—as an irrational specie that is not and cannot be bound by any moral obligations—is not someone that can be wronged. Nevertheless, in his “Metaphysics of Morals”, Kant makes a concession by offering a partial solution. When one treats animals inhumanely, they are actually weakening their intrinsic empathy towards living species in general. Part of the duties as a rational moral agent is cultivating one’s own morally good dispositions, and by mistreating animals, one could be ruining several of their positive dispositions that are “serviceable to morality” (Kant, 1797). Ultimately, animals can definitely be relevant to some extent, but necessarily indirectly. This has thus come to be known as the indirect duties.

Assumptions

I will begin my evaluation of their arguments by comparing the key underlying assumptions.

To begin with, Kant holds a relatively obvious assumption that serves as a basis for his argument, writing that “Only a rational being has the capacity to act in accordance with the representation of laws”. By arguing so, he isn’t saying that every individual is rational but rather every human has the capacity to be rational. The same applies to all moral agents (so far there’s only human)—they need the potentiality for rationality. To Kant, animals can never deserve direct moral consideration because of this, so this section will examine if animals demonstrate rational capacity from a behaviorist approach.

Four years ago, a dog named Bunny gained widespread attention on YouTube after her owner shared a series of videos displaying her ability to "communicate" fluently in English using sound buttons. In the channel, Bunny was capable of using various vocabularies in coherent sequences to form different statements and questions, such as "Bunny. Love. Mom." At this point, Kant might reject this evidence I'm providing by arguing that Bunny's actions could be interpreted as mere conditioned responses, reinforced by rewards such as a pat on the head from her owner. Yet this evidence extends further, as Bunny began to showcase self-awareness at 14 months old, just like a human child would at approximately 18 months years old. For a very long time, humans have observed the development of infants' autonomy by looking for a common set of phenomena: constantly staring into the mirror, use of verbal labels for self, and empathetic acts. These behaviors almost completely aligned with Bunny's, and here are some conversations that occurred according to the owner's video:

Mom: Say thank you love you mom

Bunny: (presses) Why. Love. What.

Mom: (Places a mirror in front of Bunny for the first time)

Bunny: (Looks into the mirror and presses) Who. This.

Fig. 1. Video posted by YouTuber *WhatAboutBunny*

Bunny's story presents an unprecedented case of an animal that receives almost the exact same education as a human child. After watching the complete scenario, we could witness Bunny

asking various logical questions. Does that reveal to us that animals possess the capacity for rational reasoning, just that they weren't ever invited to this anthropocentric game in the past? The assumption that animals possess no rational capacity at all seems easily overturned if we perceive them as potential recipients of rational education.

The assumption underlying Bentham's argument is not as explicit but is relatively more concrete than Kant's assumption regarding rationality. This assumption can be summarized in a single sentence: utility is fundamentally a psychological concept that is both quantitative and commensurable across all sentient beings. Bentham's assumption sort of enabled him to sidestep the question of animal's mental capacities that Kant struggled with.

To begin with, assuming that utility is quantifiable for all species seemingly complicates the task of measuring pleasure and pain for animals, as measuring the maximum pleasure or pain may require advanced neurometers to assess dopamine release. Nevertheless, utilitarianism allows for approximations, as demonstrated by the proposal of the hedonic calculus. In fact, there are many real-life situations where we make estimations of the total pleasure and pain that can be produced on animals. For instance, we know that scratching a cat's neck will make it happy, while dragging its tail will make it furious.

Utilitarianism compels most of us to adopt an empirical approach when considering utility for animals (except for those using a neurometer), but adapting to this process may not be as difficult as it sounds. With our developing understanding of animal behavior, the majority can easily grasp what causes pleasure or pain.

Additionally, John Stuart Mill tried to lessen these assumptions by modifying Bentham's definition of utility. He redefined utility as qualitative rather than quantitative, and categorized pleasure into higher (prioritized) and lower (too common) ones, the former being activities that engage the mind, and the latter being the animalistic ones. This modification makes significant changes to the implications of utilitarianism in animal welfare, since humans strive for higher pleasures all the time and are educated to do so, while animals weren't really "invited to this game" in history.

Although it is for a fact that both the higher and lower pleasures exist—the development of modern technology has allowed neuroscience to provide evidence which indicates the existence

of qualitative differences between pleasures. Yet, it remains hard to justify the superiority of “higher pleasures”, especially why it should be used to evaluate the pleasures of animals. Mill’s proposal may have been better limited to the calculation of human utility, rather than that of animals, as it brings forth a series of questions: why do animals show less activities of higher faculties? Can we cultivate their higher faculties? Why would we even do so? The ambiguity within Mill’s classification of pleasures seems to inversely justify for why utility, when it comes to all sentient beings, shall remain merely quantitative, at least before cultivating higher faculties within animals become a mainstream trend.

The Weak Premise Within Kant’s Indirect Duties

According to Kant, we have an indirect duty to treat animals kindly because it fosters virtuous moral traits such as compassion and empathy, which are crucial for moral development. Conversely, treating them brutally will ultimately result in the decay of one’s moral character, in turn failing to treat fellow humans with respect and dignity. Based on this reasoning, if one could draw the line very clearly between humans and animals, then they won’t be failing their dispositions. For instance, many stray animal abusers live very peacefully in human society. Kant would likely refute this by arguing that even if no “side effect” happens, the individual is still failing their duty as a moral agent of cultivating sympathy. Though this is definitely not the most convincing defense. To me, Kant presents a bit of an unrealistic expectation on the human empathy itself. His arguments demonstrate a sense of certainty regarding what “erodes” empathy and what doesn’t, yet the validity of his assumption remains problematic: if, even for a few people, the act of damaging animals’ wellbeing does not erode their sense of empathy at all, or to put it in another way, their acts of animal abuse aren’t associated with empathy, or any positive dispositions, then those people are free of the “indirect duties”. Can this provide individuals with a well-rounded justification for their abuse towards animals?

For instance, NPD (narcissistic personality disorder) is a mental illness that has been increasingly diagnosed in the past decades, with symptoms of over-exaggerated sense of self importance and extensive lack of empathy. These people live without empathy for the majority of their lives, but their rationality, as Kant claims for everyone to possess, helps them adapt to the human society like just like regular people (despite accompanied by certain difficulties), but they are capable of

acting for the sake of duty. Does this mean that NPD patients are free to abuse animals since they lack intrinsic empathy to erode?

Recent news regarding the widespread animal poisoning in Guangzhou, China has shown that many of the found poisoners have been diagnosed with NPD. I think the difficulty for Kant to refute this point lies in his lack of recognition towards animals as ends in themselves. His stance on the moral relevance of animals is overly dependent on his observation of contingent psychological facts about merely humans, which sort of creates a dilemma in his theory.

Alignment With Moral Intuitions and Social Implications

I will implement a personal perspective when examining the extent to which the two theories align with our moral intuitions, along with explanations for my views.

To begin with, Kant claims that only results of rational deliberation can be morally relevant or deserving respect. This also serves as the basis for what he addressed to be “acting for the sake of duty rather than acting in accordance with duty”, for instance, we have the duty to cultivate empathy. Intuitively, I’d definitely morally praise another individual for cultivating their empathy, yet I would to a large degree prefer for them to do so genuinely rather than doing so for the sake of duty. Putting it in another way, if someone’s emotional faculties align perfectly with their moral compass, is that individual undeserving of moral worth at all?

Consider the widely reported incident at the Cincinnati Zoo, where a three-year-old boy got severely injured after accidentally falling into a gorilla enclosure. Despite the potential danger, gorilla Binti Jua intervened. She gently carried the boy to the zookeeper’s entrance, patted him gently, and protected him from other gorillas in the enclosure.

Of course, Kant might dismiss Binti’s actions as merely a result of instincts, arguing that her behavior was driven by maternal instincts, given the physical similarities between a human child and a baby gorilla. From this perspective, her actions would lack moral intent and thus would not deserve moral praise.

Yet, the global response to Binti’s actions tells a different story. She garnered worldwide admiration and was celebrated as a hero, even earning her own Wikipedia page. The public’s

extensive respect and admiration for Binti marks a distinction between Kant’s deontological framework and the way we intuitively assign moral value to non-rational or even animalistic behaviors. This scenario doesn’t necessarily deny or object to Kant’s view which the moral worth of actions should only be limited to those of rational deliberations, yet raises a point that it might contradict with the majority’s intuitions.

Fig. 2. Screenshot of Binti’s Wikipedia page

Conversely, rather than claiming for Bentham to be an advocate for animal rights, those rights are more like the result of the animal welfare that he is promoting. Due to the fact that we consider total welfare rather than setting any sorts of distinctions between welfare of different species, animal cruelty is rejected when it offers an inefficient ratio of pleasure to pain. Take the animal show as an example: despite the possible pleasure these types of performances can bring to animals, the suffering that the animals endure behind the scenes and the freedom they’re forced to give up tremendously outweighs the total pleasure gained by humans. This is a typical scenario where utilitarians would firmly reject harming animals. What if we delve deeper and discover that the animal trainers depend on these shows for their livelihood, gaining both status and financial security to raise their families? Would animal cruelty be, to some extent, ethical in this case?

The Benthamite answer to this question is likely a “yes”, as what ultimately matters are the total possible pleasure regardless of species. Yet, if we change the animals to human babies and reconsider this scenario, would the choice of abusing babies for the financial income of a few

families be ethical? This is in fact the same objection Bentham faced in his argument for the abolition of slavery—when there are no feasible alternatives, the suffering of a few individuals can be justified for the greater good of the majority (though it isn't as convincing in the context for slavery, since the slaves should be the majority). This is just one of the scenarios that showcase the complexity of utilitarianism's implications. The root of this complexity is the intensified interrelatedness between individuals in moral decision making, to the extent that many of our rights are dependent on the interest of others.

Speciesism argument

“Because membership in the species *Homo sapiens* seems to fail to track anything ethically significant, basing worth on it seems to those who offer this argument to be unjustified discrimination against nonhumans – that is, speciesism” (Sandler 2017). Bentham makes a premise to all the potential refutations to his argument which the distinction and exclusion of other species in humans' moral system is just as reprehensible as racism. The validity of Bentham's analogy remains questionable, but that doesn't deny the tenability of speciesism in its original form (given by Singer). Hence, before evaluating Bentham's accusation, I will first examine whether Kant exhibits traits of a speciesist based on the term's literal definition.

First of all, the reason Kant is often accused of speciesism isn't necessarily because he “set the bars too high” for a being to be considered a moral agent, it is in fact quite the opposite.

If we examine the boundaries he establishes for “rationality”, we may find that these standards aren't particularly high. To be a rational being in a Kantian sense is to be capable of acting in accordance with laws and sometimes in the opposite of desires. To be a rational being in the common sense of the word is to be a being who is presently thinking things through clearly. Kant in fact had no delusions that rational beings always process things clearly. Hence, it is quite possible for a rational being in the Kantian sense to be irrational in the common sense. While this point justifies for majority of the human population to be moral agents, such as a drug addict. They are still rational beings for Kant even though not behaving in a fashion that would be considered rational in common sense. This is where the problem arises: dogs and cats can be trained to follow certain instructions—accurately and for a long period of time. This is where the

issue arises: animals like dogs and cats can be trained to follow instructions accurately and consistently. For example, a police dog can be trained to identify the scent of drug dealers and react aggressively in their presence, while remaining gentle around others. Yet apparently, Kant would consider the drug dealer a moral agent that can be morally condemned, but the police dog as a being that cannot be respected or morally praised.

On the other hand, Bentham's assertion that speciesism is as reprehensible as racism does not adequately support his main argument. He is right in claiming that before racism was eliminated, we treated skin color differences as one in kind rather than degree, just like our current view on animals: that they are inherently different and lower because of biological differences. However, a possible rebuttal to his justification would be that the differences in sentience across species do not carry the same weight as the distinctions among human races. Humans experience a broader range of pain, making them susceptible to much greater kinds of suffering. While this difference might not necessarily be substantial, especially considering the potential for animals to engage in a greater variety of activities than we conventionally expect, there exists a specific category of pain unique to humans: pain induced by social constructs. A clear example of this is the postpartum depression, which is usually evoked by a series of human exclusive events such as financial issues, relationship issues with new family members, and marital strife. The complexity of the contemporary human society had generated a variety of new triggers to pain, that makes the difference between humans' suffer and animals' suffer one of kind and not degree. Ultimately, this example does not deny the point that many philosophers' argument can be deemed of speciesism, but doubts whether speciesism can really be justified to carry the same weight as racism.

Conclusion

In all, Bentham makes a more generous assumption that is relatively justifiable and even allowed him to accuse other opposing opinions as "speciesist/anthropocentric". While for Kant, though he tried to loosen his biggest assumption by claiming that rationality for humans stands for a potentiality rather than a lifelong ability. It is difficult for him to escape the accusation of speciesism as the majority of his arguments seems to be intentionally excluding animals for the sake of doing so rather than because he has to do so.

The body of Kant's framework, specifically his proposal of indirect duties, while potentially encouraging acts of kindness for animals among certain individuals, inadvertently provides justification for acts of animal violence among those who lack the intrinsic empathy necessary to cultivate moral virtues. By addressing humans as the only beings worthy of moral consideration and respect, Kant fails to adequately justify the exclusivity of rationality as the criterion for moral status. Moreover, the implication of his argument—that only the results of rational deliberation should be morally relevant—is greatly counterintuitive. Kant's framework, therefore, invites scrutiny regarding its ability to foster a genuinely compassionate moral landscape.

As for Bentham, the connection between utilitarianism and a strong commitment to ending animal exploitation is less robust than it appears. The framework promotes impartiality among all sentient beings, yet does not inherently reject cruelty, it may even exacerbate the suffering of certain individuals for the greater good of the larger population. In turn, animal activists should not consider utilitarianism to be the most credible framework.

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